

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE BANK

RADxUP
**Community Health
Worker Symposium**
Simposio de Promotoras

Presented by RADx-UP Working Groups

Panel #1 — Engaging Hispanic/Latino/Latinx Communities

(Delivered Spanish-first with English interpretation)

Lorena Godinez
Promotora, CA

Anabel Serna
Promotora, CA

Nayeli Garcia
Promotora, NC

Edny Gonzalez
Promotora, AZ

Panel #2 – Sustaining Community Health Workers Through Policy

Kevin Nguyen
Community Health Worker, UT

Angela (Kirtdoll) Bates
Community Health Worker, OH

Senge Ngalame
Community Health Worker, GA

Vinitra Murray
Community Health Worker, OH

Benefits, Challenges, & Recommendations to Address the Challenges

Panel #1 — Engaging Hispanic/Latino/Latinx Communities

(Delivered Spanish-first with English interpretation)

Key Takeaways:

Benefits:

CHWs are the bridge between the academic institutions and communities

Building rapport is essential and an important duty for CHWs in the communities that they serve

Local training opportunities and existing social networks promote more community-based CHWs/Promotoras

Challenges:

CHWs seek resources and training on how to connect with state leaders to partner in developing better policies that are not antagonistic to certain groups (for example, immigrant families)

Recommendations to address challenges:

Empower CHWs with targeted training and resources to effectively engage state leaders, fostering inclusive policies sensitive to marginalized groups (for example immigrant families)

Benefits, Challenges, & Recommendations to Address the Challenges

Panel #2 — Sustaining Community Health Workers Through Policy

Key Takeaways:

Benefits:

CHWs are typically already active in their community and assist individuals with access to the resources they need.

Integrating CHWs into local health departments helps them provide wrap-around services.

Challenges:

CHW's role is often not considered when creating grants or policies benefiting the community. This creates gaps between the community and policymakers and undermines the role of CHWs, who are often the most knowledgeable about the community's needs.

Recommendations to address challenges:

Enhanced sustainable funding and legislative support, including certifications and improved compensation, are vital to both expanding and adequately valuing the CHW workforce in response to field demands.

Building the capacity of CHWs is essential. CHWs lacked the knowledge and training necessary to effectively educate and communicate with their communities about COVID-19.